

STROBE Statement—checklist of items that should be included in reports of observational studies

	Item No.	Recommendation	Page No.	Relevant text from manuscript
Title and abstract	1	(a) Indicate the study's design with a commonly used term in the title or the abstract	Page 1	Lines 1-2
		(b) Provide in the abstract an informative and balanced summary of what was done and what was found	Page 1-3	Line 12-39
Introduction				
Background/rationale	2	Explain the scientific background and rationale for the investigation being reported	Pages 3-6	Lines 45-108
Objectives	3	State specific objectives, including any prespecified hypotheses	Page 6	Lines 101-108
Methods				
Study design	4	Present key elements of study design early in the paper	Page 7	Lines 110-117
Setting	5	Describe the setting, locations, and relevant dates, including periods of recruitment, exposure, follow-up, and data collection	Page 7	Lines 110-117
Participants	6	<i>Cross-sectional study</i> —Give the eligibility criteria, and the sources and methods of selection of participants	Page 7-8	Lines 135-152
Variables	7	Clearly define all outcomes, exposures, predictors, potential confounders, and effect modifiers. Give diagnostic criteria, if applicable	Page 8	Lines 154-215
Data sources/ measurement	8*	For each variable of interest, give sources of data and details of methods of assessment (measurement). Describe comparability of assessment methods if there is more than one group	Page 9	Lines 164-215
Bias	9	Describe any efforts to address potential sources of bias	Page 7-9	Lines 115-161
Study size	10	Explain how the study size was arrived at	Page 8	Lines 135-152

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Quantitative variables	11	Explain how quantitative variables were handled in the analyses. If applicable, describe which groupings were chosen and why	Page 10-11	Lines 186-215
Statistical methods	12	(a) Describe all statistical methods, including those used to control for confounding	Page 12-13	Lines 186-215
		(b) Describe any methods used to examine subgroups and interactions	NA	NA
		(c) Explain how missing data were addressed	Page 8	Line 154-161
		(d) If applicable, describe analytical methods taking account of sampling strategy	NA	NA
		(e) Describe any sensitivity analyses	NA	NA
Results				
Participants	13*	(a) Report numbers of individuals at each stage of study—eg numbers potentially eligible, examined for eligibility, confirmed eligible, included in the study, completing follow-up, and analysed	Page 8-10	Lines 135-152
		(b) Give reasons for non-participation at each stage	Page 8	Lines 149-152
		(c) Consider use of a flow diagram	---	---
Descriptive data	14*	(a) Give characteristics of study participants (eg demographic, clinical, social) and information on exposures and potential confounders	Page 7	110-116
		(b) Indicate number of participants with missing data for each variable of interest	NA	NA
		<i>Cross-sectional study</i> —Report numbers of outcome events or summary measures		
Main results	16	(a) Give unadjusted estimates and, if applicable, confounder-adjusted estimates and their precision (eg, 95% confidence interval). Make clear which confounders were adjusted for and why they were included	NA	NA
		(b) Report category boundaries when continuous variables were categorized	NA	NA
		(c) If relevant, consider translating estimates of relative risk into absolute risk for a meaningful time period	NA	NA

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Other analyses	17	Report other analyses done—eg analyses of subgroups and interactions, and sensitivity analyses	NA	NA
Discussion				
Key results	18	Summarise key results with reference to study objectives	Page 13-22	Lines 216-339
Limitations	19	Discuss limitations of the study, taking into account sources of potential bias or imprecision. Discuss both direction and magnitude of any potential bias	Page 26	Lines 277-285
Interpretation	20	Give a cautious overall interpretation of results considering objectives, limitations, multiplicity of analyses, results from similar studies, and other relevant evidence	Pages 13-22	Lines 420-437
Generalisability	21	Discuss the generalisability (external validity) of the study results	Page 27	Lines 443-457
Other information				
Funding	22	Give the source of funding and the role of the funders for the present study and, if applicable, for the original study on which the present article is based	NA	NA

*Give information separately for cases and controls in case-control studies and, if applicable, for exposed and unexposed groups in cohort and cross-sectional studies.

Note: An Explanation and Elaboration article discusses each checklist item and gives methodological background and published examples of transparent reporting. The STROBE checklist is best used in conjunction with this article (freely available on the Web sites of PLoS Medicine at <http://www.plosmedicine.org/>, Annals of Internal Medicine at <http://www.annals.org/>, and Epidemiology at <http://www.epidem.com/>). Information on the STROBE Initiative is available at www.strobe-statement.org.